

Bristol Composites Institute

Differential Eddy Current Sensing
Probe and its Implementation in
Automated Composite
Manufacturing Applications

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InVIsion Carbon: Project Background

- What is Inductive sensing?
 - Eddy current testing (ECT)
 - Non-contact, non-destructive
 - Small electromagnets excite current flow within material; detect changes in the magnetic field produced by the material
- What can it do?
 - Fibre orientation, stacking sequence, local fibre volume fraction, consolidation, missing tows, sub-surface waviness.
- What is the current state of the technology?
 - Limited versatility in commercially available ECT systems
 - Limitless possible CFRP components with fixed sensor properties

InVIsion Carbon: Project Overview

- Challenge
 - In-line ECT monitoring in realistic CFRP manufacturing environments
 - Quantify and minimise noise and measurement uncertainties
 - Characterise sensitivity to material properties or features of interest
- Project Aim
 - Demonstrate and evaluate ECT on two automated manufacturing applications: **Automated Tape Laying** and **Filament Winding**
- Benefit
 - Non-contact, allowing for in-process inspection
 - High speed, applicable to industrial scale manufacturing
 - Quality monitoring, enabling early detection of manufacturing flaws
 - Improved manufacturing rates, due to reduction in inspection times

Integration of the Eddy-current probe in the ATL application

Integration of the Eddy-current probe in the FW application

Eddy Current Sensing Probe

The Eddy current sensing probe consists of three main components, including;

1. Driver coil to generate magnetic field
2. Pick-up coil to detect changes in the magnetic field, positioned in axial and transverse orientations.
3. Amplifier boards to on-board process the signal

Signal generated by the probe are transmitted to an USB oscilloscope (Handscope) and interfaced via a LABVIEW PC program over USB

Electrical integration of the Eddy current sensing probe

The Eddy current sensing probe with its key components highlighted

EC in Automated Tape Laying

Within the ATL application, the eddy current sensor was optimised and integrated into the ATL machine, and was proven to detect features including: Apparent defects (Delamination) and Subsurface defects

However, due to material availability and the project timelines, the data collection effort was shifted to the FW application.

EC Sensor integrated into the ATL Machine

Position history of Eddy current scans over defects in ATL

Filament Winding Sensing Bench

The FW Sensing Bench positioned within the cell

The operating principles of the FW Sensing Bench

A sensing bench was developed, featuring;

1. X axis for continuous movement across the liner
2. Y axis to automatically adjust the lift-off from the material surface

During scanning, the liner was continuously rotated as the probe scanned. This allowed for the complete characterisation of the liner.

Initial Defect Testing

To test the effectiveness of the sensor, samples with apparent defects were generated, featuring;

1. In-plane waviness defects generated by hex keys, which were used to create wrinkles of 0.5 to 4 mm. These wrinkles were pushed perpendicular to the fibre direction after the hex keys were removed, and covered by a secondary layer of tow-preg to create subsurface defects.
2. A pristine defect-free sample for comparison.

The samples were scanned with the sensing probe stationary and rotating the liner at a constant speed.

Generating in-plane waviness of varying sizes within the tow-preg samples

Scanning the pristine and the defective samples with the FW sensing bench stationary

Initial Defect Testing – Results

Initial calibration results showed that;

1. The data collected are repeatable across multiple runs.
2. High quality defect data can be collected up to 40 deg/s (6.67 RPM), corresponding to a linear speed of 52 mm/s.
3. The sensor response improved at operating frequencies closer to 3 MHz.
4. When the sensor is actuated as the liner rotates, the complete geometry can be scanned (continued in the next slide).

Repeatability Testing

Varying Speed

Varying Frequency

Scanning while Moving

Initial Defect Testing –Scan While Move

Significant Defects

Pristine Sample

Axial Response

Transverse Response

By actuating the sensor while rotating the liner, defects and tow structure within the geometry were identified, where;

1. It was observed that the axial sensor responded more to the major changes in the tow structure (such as gaps in-between the tows) whereas the transverse sensor responded to the in-plane waviness more.
2. Post-processing allowed for subtracting the underlying tow structure and identifying locations of defects.

Multiple Hoop Layers Deposition

Following the initial calibration, multiple hoop layers were deposited to assess the effectiveness of the sensor, where;

1. An initial hoop layer was wound around the liner and several defects were embedded, along with a reference point.
2. This initial layer with defects was covered with multiple layers (six with the first layer) to assess the effectiveness of the sensor in detecting underlying defects.

The geometry was scanned at each layer for incremental quantification, along with optimising the lift-off from the surface.

Multiple Hoop Layers

Scans of the multi-layer hoop geometry showed that;

1. Defects and tow structure visible after multilayer depositions.
2. EC response increased after multiple layers were deposited (possibly due to better contact between layers).
3. An optimum lift-off of 2.5 mm from the surface should be aimed for ideal response.

Multiple Hoop Layers Deposition

Applying post-processing to the sixth layer scan and analysing the complete geometry also showed that;

1. The axial sensor was able to identify all three defects, the reference point, and the initial tow tensioning defect even after five consecutive layers were deposited.
2. The transverse response can identify only some of the features, which could be due to the nature of the defects generated (in-plane waviness).
3. Tow structure can be subtracted by applying the post-processing to highlight only the defects.

This demonstrated the sensors capability in detecting sub-surface defects, as well as providing information regarding the nature of the defects detected.

Depositing 22 Degree Layers

Winding the 22-degree layer on the geometry

22-degree layer after deposition

Following the hoop-layer investigation, a 22-degree layer was deposited on top of the hoop layers, where;

1. The material was wound onto the liner after the technician adjusted the machine, resulting in a down-time. This could be a window to EC scans in a live implementation.
2. The wound geometry was scanned using the previous methodology.

Depositing 22 Degree Layers

Post-processing the scans after the deposition demonstrated that;

1. Several features were highlighted as defects, which could correspond to gaps, overlaps, end points of the deposition, as well as defects in the underlying layers.
2. The EC data can be used calculate deviations in the tow angles by tracing the detected features.

$$\tan^{-1} \frac{(0 - 55)}{(50 - 200)} = 0.34 \text{ rad} = \sim 20 \text{ deg}$$

Depositing 22 Degree Layers

Defect embedded in the 22-degree layer

Following this quantification, a defect was embedded in the 22-degree layer and scanned, where;

1. The embedded defect was detected both by the axial and transverse sensors.
2. The underlying tow structure was still visible within the scans.

Embedded Defect

Defect Covered with Hoop Layer

Hoop layer deposited on top of the 22-degree layer with the defect

The 22-degree layer with the defect was then covered with another hoop layer and scanned. The results showed;

1. The embedded defect was still detected by the transverse sensor, whereas the axial sensor highlighted a different feature in the 22-degree layer.
2. The 22-degree layer was still visible within the scans.

Axial Response

Transverse Response

Depositing 70 Degree

Hoop layer deposited on top of the 70-degree layer

The final two layers involved depositing a 70-degree layer, followed by another hoop layer. Final scans showed;

1. Due to the shallower angle of the 70-degree layers, the calculating the fibre orientation is more difficult. This could be improved by conducting measurements at a higher resolution.
2. The defect in the 22-degree layer was still visible within the scans.

Conclusions & Future Work

Key Lessons Learned

- The manufactured geometries during ATL and filament winding processes can be in-line characterised using EC sensors.
- Automated defect detection allows for identifying features of interest.
- The performance of EC Sensor improves as more material is deposited, especially with different fibre orientations (even when the defects are buried deeper in the material.)
- Optimum parameters were selected, improvements to make for future measurements were identified (Liftoff, frequency, sampling rate...).

Conclusions & Future Work

Continuing the trials/ Finalising the TPT Project

- Comparison with XCT Data
- Developing capabilities to characterise the tank at the domes for validating models and CAM programming (**Request from FW team**).
- In-process characterisation of a functional part e.g. hydrogen tank and/or varying process tension to create realistic defects.
- Development of the final EC probe resistant to environmental noise.
- Documenting the process within a journal article.

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Filament Winding: Software

The control software for the FW sensing bench

The control software (operating at 100 Hz) features two defect detection systems based on MIL-HDBK-1823A* , where;

1. The in-line defect detection applies frequency filtering to detect defects during the process.
2. The off-line defect detection post-processes the data to highlight defects (<10 seconds upon collecting data).

* Nondestructive evaluation system reliability assessment, Department of Defence Military Handbook (1999), 1823, MIL-HDBK-1